

Nano-Encapsulated Transethosomal Gel of Febuxostat for Improved Gout Therapy: Development and Characterization

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Abstract— When serum urate levels rise steadily, a condition known as hyperuricemia occurs, which causes monosodium urate crystals to develop and accumulate in and around the joints. This causes tissue to grow supersaturated with urate, which causes gout, a prevalent kind of joint inflammation arthritis. Even though FBX is effective, its use is restricted due to its poor water solubility and oral bioavailability, which are impacted by enzymatic degradation and co-administration with food. The oral formulation issues can be overcome by using topical transethosomal formulation. By utilizing transethosomes' affinity for skin and their capacity to penetrate the skin more deeply, these formulations provide better drug absorption. So, this study aimed to improve the efficacy of febuxostat by transethosomes (TEs) Formulation, using either ethanol injection method or thin-film hydration techniques. The prepared transethosomes were characterized for entrapment efficiency, particle size, zeta potential. In vitro characterization of the FBX-TEs optimized Soya-*lecithin*: Span 60 displayed that the 81.30% versus 66.48% entrapment efficiency, 153 nm versus 267 nm particle size, -23.9 mV versus -22.5 mV Zeta potential in the thin film hydration techniques and ethanol injection method, respectively. Hence, the thin film hydration technique is an optimized technique for preparing febuxostat transethosomes. The optimized transethosomal formulation was then incorporated into a gel prepared with 1% Carbopol 934 it demonstrated 84.04% in vitro drug release and better antibacterial activity as compared to standard (pure) febuxostat. Overall, the use of transethosomal gel formulation is a highly effective method for administering drugs through the skin.

Keywords— Nanotechnology, Thin film hydration techniques, Ethanol injection method, Transdermal drug delivery, Drug release.

I. INTRODUCTION

When monosodium urate crystals (MSU) accumulate in the tissues, it cause gout, a systemic condition. Uric acid crystals are mostly caused by elevated serum uric acid (SUA) exceed a certain threshold. Although MSU crystals can grow in various tissues, they are most frequently found in and around joints, where they form tophi [1]. Treatment for gout that aims to avoid attacks and other signs by lowering the blood urate level is not the same as treatment for an acute attack [2]. Gout is treated with drug therapy, including NSAIDs, analgesics, colchicine, corticosteroids, uricosurics and xanthine oxidase inhibitors, recommended to the American college of Rheumatology [3]. Although xanthine oxidase inhibitors work effectively in the treatment of renal failure, because renal processes are predominantly responsible for their clearance, these patients may need to have their dosage reduced. Because xanthine oxidase inhibition lowers uric acid generation in humans, it is recommended for the treatment of hyperuricemia and associated disease, such as gout.

Febuxostat (FBX), a new and powerful non-purine selective xanthine oxidase inhibitor, demonstrates superior efficacy over than allopurinol for reducing and sustaining serum urate levels. When food is present, febuxostat's oral bioavailability decreases to 38%. Because febuxostat is poorly soluble in water (less than 15 g/ml) and undergoes substantial enzymatic breakdown in liver and gastrointestinal tract, its oral bioavailability is limited. Additionally, when food is present, the highest plasma concentration (C_{max}) of febuxostat decreases by 38-49%. Among febuxostat drawbacks include its low bioavailability, gut-wall metabolism, food-dependent absorption, gastrointestinal disorders [4]. Transdermal distribution of the medication will circumvent all of these issues related to the currently marketed version. These problems are resolved by transethosomal formulation, which permits prolonged therapeutic action. For the treatment of severe forms of arthritis and persistent gout, febuxostat is the FDA-approved drug of choice.

Lipid-based suspensions including niosomes, liposomes, microemulsion are additionally suggested as low-risk drug carriers; however, because they only penetrate the epidermis' outermost layers, they are not very useful for transdermal drug administration. Transethosomes (TEs) are a recently developed lipid-based vesicular system that exhibits improved drug penetration through the skin for transdermal drug administration [5]. First-pass metabolism is avoided, making TEs more biocompatible and biodegradable, non-toxic, more stable, and patient compliance. Most recent research has examined TEs, a

unique class of nanovesicles. They are lipid nanovesicles that combine the benefits of ethosomes and transfersomes, making them malleable, stable, flexible, and biodegradable materials. Because permeation enhancers are present, TEs are able to more efficiently penetrate the stratum corneum [6]. Transethosomes have been used in a number of trials to improve the dermal/transdermal distribution of different medications. By employing a transethosomes formulation through the transdermal route, the undesirable side effects linked to oral drug administration can be successfully reduced.

The aim of this research Transethosomes is a targeted drug delivery technology that enables regulated medication distribution. Transethosomal gel compositions change the kinetics of drug release, improve bioavailability, and lessen FBX adverse effects. This innovative approach utilizes the lipophilic properties of febuxostat and the enhanced skin penetration capabilities of transethosomes to achieve optimal therapeutic outcomes. In this study, FBX-TEs were created and evaluated for encapsulation efficiency (EE), ζ -potential, and particle size. The optimal FBX-TEs formulation was then added to a gel system with Carbopol 934 acting as a gelling agent. The potential efficacy of the fabricated febuxostat transethosomal gel was assessed by evaluating its viscosity, antimicrobial efficacy, and in vitro drug release.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Materials

Excel Industries LTD (Ratnagiri, India) provided FBX as a gift sample. Soya-lecithin, Span 60, Tween 80, Carbopol 934, Propylene glycol, Triethanolamine, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, Disodium hydrogen phosphate, Sodium chloride, and Dialysis membrane were purchased from Research-Lab Fine Chem Industries (Mumbai, India).

Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FT-IR) Spectroscopy

FBX's infrared spectra were analyzed with a Shimadzu IR Affinity-1S CE Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer. The FTIR spectra of Carbopol 934, phospholipid, surfactant, and pure drugs were captured using 20 scans on an IR spectrophotometer between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} [7].

B. Methods of Preparation of FBX-loaded Transethosomes

1) Thin film hydration technique (TFH)

Thin film hydration /rotary film evaporation technique was used to produce transethosomes by using Rotary – Evaporator instrument (Superfit Rotavap – PBU 6D Mumbai, India). Transethosomes of Febuxostat were made by dissolving a specific quantity of the drug, soya lecithin, and edge activators in ethanol (30 % v/v), an organic solvent, in a round bottom flask. A thin layer was formed inside the flask wall by evaporating the solvent at 60°C and rotating it at 60 rpm for one hour. After that, the film was hydrated with a 20 ml ethanol-containing phosphate-buffered saline solution, and it was left overnight to create multilamellar vesicles. Sonication was then used to produce smaller unilamellar vesicles. After being sonicated, the vesicles were extruded through a polycarbonate membrane to create transethosomes [7]. As shown in Table I, several formulations were made with varying quantities of soya lecithin and edge activators. The formulation process is displayed in Fig 1.

2) Ethanol injection method (EI)

The ethanol injection method was used to prepare the transethosomes formulations. In brief, a precisely measured quantity of soya lecithin, edge activators, and drug dissolved in ethanol (alcoholic phase). The system was sealed tightly to prevent ethanol from evaporating. Using a syringe pump and continuous stirring at 500 rpm and 25°C for an hour, the aqueous phase was gradually administered into the ethanol until the total volume reached 20 mL. The resulting dispersion was then subjected to sonication for four cycles of 5 min, with a 3-minute break in between, and stored at 4°C for further study [8]. Table I presents various formulations, while Fig 1 illustrates the formulation process.

Fig 1. Transethosomes formulation Methodology A) Thin film hydration Techniques B) Ethanol injection Method

Table I. Composition of the FBX-loaded transethosomes vesicles

Formulation Code	Drug (mg)	Soya- lecithin (mg)	Edge activators	
			Span 60 (%)	Tween 80 (%)
TE1	100	100	5	-
TE2	100	200	10	-
TE3	100	300	15	-
TE4	100	400	20	-
TE5	100	100	-	5
TE6	100	200	-	10
TE7	100	300	-	15
TE8	100	400	-	20

C. Evaluation of formulated FBX-loaded transethosomes vesicles

1) % Entrapment Efficiency (% EE)

Entrapment Efficiency of prepared Febuxostat transethosomes was expressed in terms of the percentage of the total amount of drugs from in the transethosomes and this was done using an indirect method. Transethosomes suspension was centrifuged (REMI C-24 Plus) at 10,000 rpm at 4°C for 30 minutes in order to isolate the trapped drug from the unbound drug [9]. Using a UV spectrometer (Shimadzu®, Japan) configured to measure at 315 nm, the Supernatant was recovered and analyzed spectrophotometrically.

The EE% was computed using the accompanying formula:

$$EE\% = \left[\frac{(\text{Total amount of drug added} - \text{Free drug})}{\text{Total amount of drug added}} \right] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2) Particle Size Analysis and Polydispersity index (PDI)

The particle size analysis and polydispersity index (PDI) of the created transethosomes dispersions were evaluated utilizing dynamic light scattering technology on a Malvern Nano ZS device (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Malvern, UK) and nanoparticle analyzer (HORIBA Nanopartica SZ-100) at a temperature of 25 ±2°C. Using Milli-Q water, the transethosomal dispersion were diluted 1:10 (v/v) before analysis to reduce the impact of repeated scattering. After that, the diluted sample was put into disposable polystyrene cuvettes, put into the Zeta sizer, and quantified [10].

3) Zeta Potential measurement

The zeta potential value of the optimized formulation was determined to assess its stability. To find the zeta potential, zeta-sizer was utilized. Samples were diluted with Mili-Q water prior to analysis, and all findings were confirmed 3 times [11].

4) Vesicle Morphology - Transmission Electron microscopy (TEM)

The analysis of optimized transethosomes was employed using Tecnai 12 G2 Spirit TEM (FEI, Netherlands) that had rated at 120kV. The transethosomes dispersion was applied as a thin layer onto a carbon-coated copper grid, stained with (1%) phosphotungstic acid, and subsequently observed and photographed. The Gatan Microscopy Suite (GMS3) was used to process the images [12].

D. Preparation of FBX loaded transethosomes nanogel

Transethosomes gel was made by the dispersion technique. The optimal formulation (TE3) was taken and added to the gel formulation using 0.5-2% Carbopol®934 as the gelling agent for varying amounts based on the results of the characterization of the generated Febuxostat transethosomes preparation. An appropriate quantity of Carbopol®934 was added to the distilled water while it was continuously agitated using a magnetic stirrer (REMI 1 MLH, International Scientific Instrument, Co., Delhi, India). Overnight soaking and hydration were then applied to the combination. After that, the appropriate quantity of medication trapped in a transethosomes was added, and additional substances, such as 10% propylene glycol and methyl paraben, were added and dispersed evenly while being constantly stirred. After the gel was brought to a pH of 7 (the ideal pH for the skin) with triethanolamine, distilled water was used to change the last weight. The prepared gel was sonicated and allowed to sit overnight [12]. A pure drug dispersion was created for comparison without transethosomes or enhancers [13]. The table of gel formulas is presented in Table II.

Table II. The composition of transethosomes gel utilizing varying concentrations of Carbopol 934

Formulation code	TE3G1	TE3G2	TE3G3	TE3G4
Carbopol 934 (%w/w)	0.5	1	1.5	2
Propylene glycol (%w/w)	10	10	10	10
Methyl paraben (%w/w)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Triethanolamine	q. s	q. s	q. s	q. s
Distilled water	Up to 100	Up to 100	Up to 100	Up to 100

E. Evaluation of FBX-loaded transethosomal nanogel

1) Assessment of pH, homogeneity and grittiness

A digital pH meter (Equiptronics EQ 610, Mumbai, India) was used to measure the pH of each gel after dissolving 1 gram of gel in 25 ml of distilled water. After calibrating the electrode with pH 4.0 and pH 7.0 solutions, the electrode was measured using the pH meter. The prepared Transethosomal gels were inspected for the presence of extraneous fibers and particles, as well as for clarity, color, and uniformity. Grittiness was assessed under a microscope to find any particles that had not dissolved in the gel matrix [14].

2) Assessment of extrudability and spreadability

The gel mixtures were packaged in aluminium collapsible tubes or collapsible metal tubes. The materials were extruded by pushing the tube, and the formulation's extrudability was tested. The spreadability of a wooden block and glass slide configuration was determined using a changed version of the same. The formula used to calculate the spreadability was:

$$S = \frac{(M \times L)}{T} \quad (2)$$

Where, S is the Spreadability, M is the upper slide's weight, L is the length of the glass slide in centimetres, T is the time (s) required to separate the slides [15].

3) Assessment of viscosity measurement and % drug content

The gel's viscosity was measured in centipoises (cps) using a Brookfield (DV2T Viscometer, Brookfield Engineering Laboratories, Middleboro, MA, USA) equipped with RheocalcT 1.2.19 software. During the experiment, the temperature was kept at 25°C, and the samples were given five minutes to acclimate before being examined with Spindle 64. One gram of gel was taken out and sonicated after being mixed with 100 ml of ethanol. A UV visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800) at 315 nm was used to measure the drug content of dilutions made from the sonicate solution [9].

4) In-vitro Diffusion study

In vitro drug release evaluation was performed for all transethosomal gel batches. Subsequently, the optimized FBX-loaded transethosomal gel (TE3G2) was tested for *in vitro* drug released in comparison to FBX-loaded transethosomes vesicle and pure drug dispersion was examined used a Franz diffusion cell with PBS (pH 7.4) in the receptor chamber, kept at 37 ± 0.5 °C with constant stirring at 100 RPM. An amount of 1 g of gel was present in the donor compartment, with 1 ml samples were periodically removed and replaced with an equivalent amount of buffer (pH 7.4). After being removed at specified time intervals for 8 hours, the necessary sample was measured for febuxostat content using UV spectrophotometry at 314 nm [16] [17].

5) Drug release kinetics modelling

The mechanisms of release and the design of mathematical models for therapeutic devices are extensively used. The *in vitro* release profile of the formulations was examined by incorporating the right release data into a number of drug release models including first order (log cumulative percentage drug vs. time), zero order kinetics (cumulative quantity of drug unreleased vs. time), Korsmeyer-peppas model (log cumulative percentage drug released vs. log time) and matrix model (cumulative percentage drug released vs square root of time) [17].

6) Antimicrobial Activity

This study sought to validate the improved therapeutic effectiveness of FBX-loaded transethosomes gels because Febuxostat has an antimicrobial effect. The cylinder cup method was used to assess the preparations' antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram-negative). By assessing the inhibition of bacterial growth under controlled conditions, the cylinder cup method is frequently used to evaluate bacterial sensitivity or resistance to different antimicrobial drugs. The bacterial cultures for the test were carefully and consistently distributed over Muceller-Hinton agar plates. The test substances were added to wells made in the agar after bores were made in it. For testing, a 100 mg/ml concentration was administered to each formulation. The plates were incubated for twenty-fours at 37°C. The efficacy of the formulations was assessed by comparing the results of measurements of antibacterial activity, which was represented by a clear zone [18].

7) Stability Studies

The stability tests are being conducted in accordance with ICH recommendations. According to the rules set forth by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), the prepared formulation was kept in a stability chamber at room temperature ($40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\% \pm 5\%$ RH) and storage refrigerated condition ($4^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $65 \pm 5\%$ RH). After 30,60 and 90 days, the samples were examined for a number of factors [9] [18].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Ultraviolet Visible (UV-Vis) Spectrophotometry

UV spectrophotometry determined the λ_{max} of Febuxostat at 315 nm in ethanol and 314 nm in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), with calibration curves created in both solvents.

B. FTIR studies

The FTIR spectrum of pure Febuxostat drug resembled the drug's usual spectrum, with the highest peak linked to the drug in the spectrum of the drug and excipient. FTIR analysis confirmed compatibility between the drug and excipient, showing no interaction.

Fig 2. FTIR results Pure drug (Febuxostat)

Fig 3. FTIR results optimized formulation of TEs-Gel

C. Entrapment efficiency (% EE)

Entrapment efficiency was calculated by TE1-TE8 formulations of both the methods given in (Fig 3). The formulations entrapment efficiency ranged from 50% to 81%, with the TE3 batch (Soya lecithin: Span 60) showing the highest efficiency of 81.30% via thin film hydration techniques. Accordingly, TE3 was determined to be the optimal batch, as shown in Fig 3. The entrapment efficiency of the optimized batch span 60 is higher to that of the tween 80. This is because a span 60 with an HLB value of 4.7 will entrap more lipophilic drugs (febuxostat) due to its increased lipophilicity.

Fig 4. Comparisons of % Entrapment efficiency of Transethosomal formulations

D. Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM)

Transethosomes were spherical in shape and ranged in size from 100 to 300 nm, according to TEM image of the organisms shown in Fig 5.

Fig 5. TEM images for FBX-loaded Transethosomal vesicles A) TE3-TFH B) TE2-EI

E. Vesicle size distribution and polydispersity index (PDI)

The optimized transethosomal batch TE3 (Soya lecithin: Span 60) prepared by the thin film hydration technique exhibited a vesicle size of 153 nm with a PDI of 0.235, while TE2 (Soya lecithin: Span 60) obtained using the ethanol injection method showed a vesicle size of 267 nm with a PDI of 0.289; both formulations showed a homogeneous size distribution. As shown in fig 6. Polydispersity index (PDI), which has values <0.3 for homogeneity and >0.3 for heterogeneity, demonstrates particle size uniformity.

Fig 6. Vesicle size distribution and PDI of optimized Transethosomal vesicles A) TE3-TFH B) TE2-EI

F. Zeta potential Measurement

A zeta sizer was employed to analyze the zeta potential of all formulation. Among all formulations, the optimized transethosomal batch TE3 (Soya lecithin: Span 60) formulation via thin film hydration techniques was found to be -23.9 mV value and TE2 (Soya lecithin: Span 60) by ethanol injection method was -22.5 mV value These negative values indicate high stability and reduced aggregation, enhancing long-term stability (Fig 7).

Fig 7. Zeta potential of Optimized Febuxostat loaded Transethosomal vesicles A) TE3-TFH B) TE2-EI

G. Optimization batch of transethosomes

Previously, works have been done for the preparation of Transethosomes containing Febuxostat for topical drug delivery using **Soya lecithin and Span 60**. In the present work, the optimized formulations (**TE3 and TE2**) prepared by both the methods and **TE3** formulation by thin film hydration were incorporated into 1% Carbopol gel.

H. Evaluation of Transethosomal gel

1) pH, Homogeneity and Grittiness

The transethosomal nanogels exhibited pH values ranging from 7.08 to 7.32, indicating their suitability for topical use without skin irritation. The TE3G2 formulation showed improved homogeneity compared to other formulations, with no observable grittiness or particle debris under an optical microscope, confirming its topical applicability. Results are detailed in Table III.

2) Extrudability and Spreadability

Extrudability ranged from 82.67% to 94.26% for all formulations, with TE3G2 exhibiting the highest extrudability. TE3G2 and TE3G4 also demonstrated superior spreadability, while spreadability of TE3G1 and TE3G3 was substantially reduced. Results are shown in the Table III.

3) Viscosity and % Drug content

The TE3G2 formulation demonstrated optimal viscosity for topical applications, unlike other formulations that varied in viscosity due to Carbopol 934 amounts. It also had the highest drug content at 82.43%, indicating uniform distribution in the transethosomal gels, with drug content ranging from 63.25% to 82.43% as shown in Table III.

4) Gel strength

All formulations exhibited good gel strength, with values ranging from 30 to 44 seconds, as indicated in Table III.

Table III. Evaluation of Transethosomal gel formulations

Formulation code	pH	Viscosity (Centipoise)	Spreadability (g.cm/sec ⁻¹)	Extrudability (%)	% Drug content	Gel strength (s)
TE3G1	7.08	42,256	47.95±0.43	85.45±1.43%	72.45±0.55%	30
TE3G2	7.12	36.267	74.9±0.54	94.26±2.31%	82.43±0.82%	34
TE3G3	7.20	32,357	50.44±0.17	82.67±0.25%	74.57±0.63%	42
TE3G4	7.16	43,156	72.31±0.19	92.24±2.78%	63.25±0.79%	44

The values are the mean of three readings (n=3) ± SD.

5) *In vitro* diffusion study

TF3G2 showed superior diffusion as compared to other formulations, obtaining approximately 84.04% drug release (Fig 8). The optimized transthesomal gel (TF2G2) demonstrated superior *in vitro* diffusion compared to both the transthesomal dispersion and the pure drug solution, with the TF3G2 transthesomal gel showing the best diffusion results. Because of its exceptional performance, TE3G2 was chosen as the best formulation and then put through stability and antibacterial tests.

Table IV. *In vitro* drug release values of formulation mean ± SD (n=3).

Formulation code	% <i>In vitro</i> drug release
TE3G1	80.13±1.28%
TE3G2	84.04±1.19%
TE3G3	78.29±0.34%
TE3G4	72.67±1.32%

Fig 8. *In vitro* drug release of Transthesomal gel

Fig 9. Comparative study *In Vitro* drug released a) Standard (pure) febusostat b) FBX-Transthesomal vesicles c) FBX-Transthesomal gel

Kinetic drug release

Kinetic modelling demonstrated Higuchi diffusion control ($R^2 = 0.9887$) for TF3G2, with 1% Carbopol 934 gel exhibiting ideal topical administration properties.

Fig 10. Zero order kinetic model of optimized FBX-loaded transethosomal gel

6) Antimicrobial activity

The antibacterial activity of Febuxostat were investigated against two bacterial strains, one Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and one Gram-negative (*E. coli*), as shown in Table V. Disc diffusion was used to test the bacteria susceptibility. Fig 11 shows how effective these formulations are against microorganism. According to the findings, Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*) were more vulnerable to the effect of inhibition of the FBX-loaded transethosomal gel than Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*). The inhibitory efficacy of TE3G2 formulations was higher than that of the pure drug solution. The TE3G2 formulation has the strongest antibacterial efficacy among them.

Table V. Antibacterial activity of Transethosomal gel formulation

Zone of inhibition (mm)			
No.	Formulation	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
1	TE3G2	36	32
2	Standard (pure) febuxostat	21	23

Fig 11.: Comparative *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of standard (pure) febuxostat dispersion and FBX transethosomal gel on a) *S. aureus* b) *E. coli*

7) Stability study

According to ICH guidelines, the Transethosomal gel's stability over a three-month period did not significantly changes the optimal formulation. Table VI presents the results in detail.

Table VI. Stability Studies

Optimized formulation	TF3G2				
	Initial	Room temperature (25°C± 2°C & 65 ± 5% RH)		Refrigerated condition (4°C± 2°C & 65 ± 5% RH)	
Time intervals (day)	0	30	90	30	90
pH	7.32	7.30	7.28	7.29	7.24
Drug content	82.43%	80.16%	79.89%	80.14%	79.46%
% In vitro release	84.04%	83.62%	83.22%	82.48%	82.16%

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Transethosomes of drug febuxostat were successfully prepared using the thin film hydration technique and ethanol injection method using drug, soya lecithin, span 60 and tween 80. On the basis of comparative evaluation of both the method. Thin film hydration technique containing surfactant span 60 was an optimized technique for the preparation of febuxostat transethosomes, exhibited better entrapment efficiency 81.30%, a minimal particles size 153 nm, and zeta potential of -23.9 mV. When optimized formulation (TE3) were incorporated to 1% Carbopol gel, the transethosomal nanogel demonstrated an 82.43% drug content and improved *in vitro* release (84.04% over 8 hours) in comparison to transethosomes dispersions and standard (pure) febuxostat. When comparison to the standard (pure) febuxostat, the improved formulation showed strong antibacterial efficacy against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. According to research, transethosomal gel (TE3G2) loaded with Febuxostat is better to standard drug in treating gout because it offers sustained delivery, increased bioavailability, and better patient compliance. In conclusion, the vesicular transethosomal delivery method may improve the safety and therapeutic effectiveness of medications.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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